

SYNOPSIS/ PREPHASE

Assessment of Employee engagement practices in the service sector - A study in Mangaluru city of Karnataka

INTRODUCTION

The challenge today is not about retaining talented people, but fully engaging them, capturing their minds and hearts at every stage of their career. Employee engagement has become apparent as a crucial driver of business success in today's competitive environment. Further, employee engagement could be the deciding factor for organizational success. Not only the engagement has the potential to significantly affect employee retention, productivity and loyalty, it is also a link to customer satisfaction, company reputation and overall brand image of the company. Thus, to gain a competitive edge, organizations are turning to human resources practices and practitioners to set the agenda for commitment and employee engagement.

Employee engagement is defined as "the extent to which employees are committed to something or someone in their organization, how hard they are working and how long they stay as a result of that commitment." Research has indicated that the connection between an employee's job and organizational strategy, including understanding how important the job is to the firm's success, is the most prominent driver of employee engagement.

A company with "high" employee engagement might be expected to outperform and reach excellence than those with "low" employee engagement, all other things being equal. Therefore, the employee engagement is an organizational approach, which results in the right conditions for all employees of an organization to give their best every day, committed to the organization's values, goals and objectives, motivated to contribute to organizational mission, along with increased sense of their own well-being. Employee engagement is also based on mutual trust, integrity, and mutual commitment from an organization and the employees and to bring transparency in the organization. It is a modern approach the organizations adopt which intends to increase the chances of contributing to organizational and individual performance, business success productivity and well-being of both organization and individuals.

Research Gap: The review of literature has several insights to the concept of employee engagement. The inference drawn from all studies is that employee engagement is a very important aspect, particularly in the service sector. It has been observed in many studies that there is a linkage between employee engagement and organisational performance in terms of profitability, customer satisfaction and overall growth and sustainability of an organisation. This research is an attempt to combine the three sectors namely education, banking and insurance to study employee engagement. A study of this nature was not identified in the review of literature. This study would further provide sufficient information on determine if nature of work influences strongly on employee engagement. It is an attempt to identify if same factors influence employee engagement in the different sectors in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada. Mangalore is a hub of the above mentioned services, and the people of this region have their own characteristics. The study thus is an attempt to determine the engagement levels (%) particular to the three sectors and group factors as similar and dissimilar in the sectors studied. The research further has attempted to identify the strength of association of the various factors of engagement and proceed towards a regression model. Since a study of this nature has not been conducted in Mangalore city of DK with respect to the three sectors, this would definitely add value to the knowledge of employee engagement theoretically and would be useful in driving engagement in the organisations.

The research design is **exploratory cum descriptive in nature**. The major emphasis of this study then, is on identification of engagement levels in the various service sectors and to develop a predictive model for employee engagement. The theoretical framework of the study attempts to identify various factors which influence employee engagement. The factors or constructs that influence engagement can be categorized under three heads namely individual, group (team) and organizational. Sub factors within each of the constructs have been developed namely;

- ❖ Organizational leadership and planning.
- ❖ Organizational culture and communication.
- ❖ Organizational pay and benefits.
- ❖ Organizational training and development.
- ❖ Individuals work environment.
- ❖ Individual's role in the organization.

- ❖ Relationship with Immediate supervisors.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada in India is a hub of service sector. Therefore, the proposed research study has the following objectives.

- To identify the employee engagement levels in the service sector namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.
- To build a decision rule to enable the classification of employees into one of the two groups, that is engaged or disengaged in each of these sectors.
- To explore the drivers [Factors] of employee engagement in the service sector, namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.
- To compare the three service sectors in term of employee engagement.
- To develop a relationship model for employee engagement and its causal factors for each of the three sectors.

Hypothesis for Research objective 1

To identify the employee engagement levels in the service sector namely Banking, Insurance and Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

- ❖ H₁: There is a significant difference in the level of engagement in the various service sectors namely Banking, Insurance, Education in Mangalore city of Dakshina Kannada.

Hypothesis for Research objective 2

To develop a relationship model for employee engagement and its causal factors for each of these three sectors.

- ❖ H₂: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₃: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₄: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and gender in the Education sector.

- ❖ H₅: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₆: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₇: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and length of service in the Education sector.
- ❖ H₈: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₉: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₁₀: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and age in the Education sector.
- ❖ H₁₁: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Banking sector.
- ❖ H₁₂: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Insurance sector.
- ❖ H₁₃: There is a significant relationship between employee engagement and salary in the Education sector.

SAMPLING

For this study, 1312 members constitute the sampling units, with a split of 459 employees in the education sector, 413 in the Banking sector and 440 employees in the Insurance sector. Since equal importance is given to each of these sectors 25% employees of the sampling frame is chosen as the sampling size.

Sample Inclusion

Banking: Middle level employees. Scale 1 and 2 and office staff.

Insurance: General and health Insurance [Sales head and Agents].

Education: Faculty of Basic Under graduation courses.

A quota sampling technique is used in this study. Since the response rate was 84%, 364 completed questionnaires were collected and analyzed for the research study.

The response obtained from the employees has been coded and entered into the software as per the requirements of the objectives. The data is analyzed using SPSS Version 21. Descriptive statistics like mean, median, mode, range, standard deviation, percentage, cumulative percentage have been used. Also, inferential statistics like Chi-Square, ANOVA, correlation coefficient, factor analysis, curve estimation and Discriminant analysis is used in the study

Discriminant Analysis is used to classify respondents into two categories namely engaged and disengaged. The form of equation for a three variable discriminant analysis used was

$$Y=a+K_1X_1+K_2X_2+K_3X_3$$

Where Y is the dependent variable and X₁, X₂ and X₃ are independent variables a, K₁, K₂, and K₃ are constant and coefficients. The individual factors for classifying the employee into two categories are namely age, gender, length of service and salary. The discriminant scores are calculated for each of the respondents and a decision rule for prediction is arrived at. The analysis is done separately for each of the sectors.

Also factor analysis is applied and data reduction was done in order to formulate and draft a new questionnaire to each of the sectors.

MAJOR FINDINGS.

The purpose of this study was to examine Employee Engagement in the service sector namely Indian Banking sector, Indian insurance sector, and Indian education sector since these sectors are booming and plenty of employment opportunities lay here. These sectors have contributed to the Indian economic growth. The study has further provided sufficient information on to determine if nature of work influences strongly on employee engagement.

Engagement is seen highest in the banking sector and least in the insurance sector. The banking sector has transformed rapidly and India is marching towards a digitalized banking era. The insurance sector has seen disengagement among its employees. The work culture, nature of job and targets which are assigned are the main reason for disengagement.

Comparison of gender across the three sectors shows that the insurance sector is dominated by the male gender, followed by the banking sector and then the education sector. On a closer

inspection we still see gender disparity in the insurance and banking sector when it comes to the middle and top-level management.

Median age of the respondents in the insurance sector is 26 years while the median age in the banking and education sector is 28 years. The insurance sector has a younger generation of workers when compared to the banking and education sector.

The percentage of engaged workforce is 72.3% in banking followed by education sector which is 68.4 % and least in the insurance sector which is 31.3%.

Length of service in the organization showed the highest for the banking sector followed by the education sector and finally Insurance sector.

It is observed that age is the best predictor followed by salary then followed by length of service and the last factor is gender in the banking sector.

In the education sector salary is the best predictor followed by age, then length of service and finally gender. Also, discriminant equations and regression equations are elaborated in the study and the values of the same are annexed.

Sector

Equation

Banking

$$Y = -6.282 - 0.135X_1 + 1.406X_2 + 0.073X_3 + 0.000077X_4$$

Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -6.282 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.135, 1.406, 0.073, 0.000077 for length of service, gender, age, salary.

Insurance sector

$$Y = -2.940 - 0.124X_1 + 0.000128X_2 + 0.200X_3 + 2.844X_4$$

Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -2.940 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.124, 0.000128, 0.200, 2.844 for age, salary, length of service and gender.

Education Sector

$$Y = -11.070 - 0.479X_1 + 0.643X_2 + 0.273X_3 + 0.000125X_4$$

Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -11.070 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.479, 0.643, 0.273, 0.000125 for length of service, gender, age and salary.

Overall service sector

$$Y = -4.652 - 0.000125X_1 + 0.001X_2 + 1.460X_3 - 0.047X_4$$

Where Y is the dependent variable [Engagement], -4.652 is the constant and the respective co-efficient are -0.001, 0.000125, -0.047 and 1.460 for age, salary, length of service and gender.

The above equations help in classifying respondents to one of the groups namely engaged or disengaged.

The Number of factors elicited after the process of factor analysis is 15 for banking, 26 for insurance and 20 for the education sector. This factor reduction process has helped in drafting a new questionnaire for each of the service sector on the topic of Employee Engagement. This is a great boon for further research in this area.

The concept of Curve Estimation has been used to predict engagement levels by considering the individual factors in each of the Service sectors.

CONCLUSION

It is observed that there is a clear association between engagement levels and the various sectors. Individual factors which influence employee engagement in the various sectors are elaborated and their contributions are dealt in detail. Further the concept of factor analysis is applied to extract the most important factors contributing to employee engagement in each of these sectors. Also, the personal opinion of respondents was complied with and certain strategic recommendations are drawn from the study.